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ABSTRACT

An analytical review of the methods of controlling the balance of the rocking machine of the rod deep-pumping installation for oil production (SHPU) is given is presented, which determines its technical condition. A classification of methods for balancing a pumping machine is proposed according to two criteria: the type of mechanical implementation and the method of diagnosing (identifying) the state of balance.

Existing methods for controlling balance are analyzed with a special emphasis on wattmeterographic methods, assessing their advantages and disadvantages.

Taking into account the intellectualization of the process of mechanized oil production, prospective directions for the development of methods for balancing pumping machines using sensorless control methods for SHPU are considered, in particular the power integration method, the use of intelligent controllers (SSRP), artificial intelligence algorithms and dynamic modeling.

Keywords: balance of the rocking machine, control methods, dynamogram, wattmeter, classification, controller, algorithm, artificial intelligence, model.

Introduction. Rod-type deep well pumping units (SHPU) remain the main means of mechanized oil production, especially in depleted oil fields, which cover a significant part of the wells [1,2,3]. Their prevalence is due to their reliability and ease of operation.

However, the efficiency and durability of these units critically depend on the correct balancing of the pumping unit. Proper balancing is a fundamental factor for achieving energy efficiency and extending the service life of the equipment.

Operation in an unbalanced state leads to high peak loads on the gearbox, which is the most expensive component of the unit, accounting for about 50% of capital costs, a decrease in the efficiency of the electric drive of the pumping unit motor and excessive electricity consumption [1,2,4]. Thus, in an unbalanced state, the asynchronous motor operates with a low power factor ($\cos\phi$) and low efficiency, which negatively affects the electrical network. At the same time, optimal balancing allows you to reduce the installed engine power by 80% and reduce electricity consumption by 10.5–50% [5].

Unbalance increases the stress in the rod column, which leads to a 3-fold increase in the frequency of breakages when the degree of balance deviates by only 8%. The main goal of balancing is to ensure the most uniform load on the electric drive of the rocking machine throughout the entire rocking cycle [2,6].

The purpose of the article. Conducting an analytical review of existing methods of balance control, assessing their advantages and disadvantages, as well as studying promising areas of development with a special emphasis on wattmeterographic and sensorless methods of control of SHPU.

Main material.

Classification and basics of balancing methods.

The physical essence of the balancing process is to compensate for the cyclic loads acting on the drive of

the rocker during the full working cycle. During the upward stroke of the rods, the drive overcomes the weight of the column of rods and the column of liquid, which creates a significant torque on the gearbox. During the downward stroke, the weight of the rods, on the contrary, helps the movement, creating a moment in the opposite direction. According to the classical theory, the balancing of the VC is carried out by installing additional masses (counterweights) [7,8]. Counterweights installed on the cranks accumulate potential energy during the downward stroke and give it away during the upward stroke, thereby equalizing the load on the drive and gearbox.

The central indicator of the system condition is the net torque on the gearbox. Depending on the ratio of peak loads during the up and down strokes, three main system states are distinguished [9]:

- Rod imbalance ("underbalanced" or "rod heavy"): Occurs when the peak load (and, consequently, torque) during the up stroke is significantly higher than the peak value during the down stroke. This indicates insufficient mass or suboptimal position of the counterweights.

- Counterweight imbalance ("overbalanced" or "weight heavy"): Characterized by a situation when the peak load during the down stroke is higher. This means that the counterweights are too heavy or are located too far from the axis of rotation.

- Balanced state: The ideal state in which the peak torque values during the up and down strokes are approximately the same. This minimizes the amplitude of the load fluctuations on the gearbox and drive motor.

Improper balancing, regardless of its type, leads to serious negative consequences. An increase in peak torque on the gearbox not only exceeds its nominal characteristics, which accelerates metal fatigue and gear wear, but also causes significant fluctuations in

power consumption. This leads to reduced energy efficiency, increased peak currents in the motor and increased electricity costs. Thus, achieving optimal balance is critical for reliable and economical operation of the installation, which necessitates the use of accurate methods for assessing its condition.

Based on the analysis of sources, balancing methods can be classified according to two criteria: the type of mechanical implementation (Table 1) and the method of diagnosing (identifying) the state of balance (Table 2).

Table 1

Methods of balancing a rocking machine by type of mechanical implementation

Balancing type	Mechanism description	Main characteristics
Beam Counterbalance [10]	Loads are mounted on the rear end of the balancer	The simplest and oldest method; used for small loads
Crank Counterbalance [10,11]	Counterweights are placed directly on the cranks	The most common type for modern VCs; allows for fine tuning
Compound Balancin [9]	Combination of weights on the balancer and crank	Provides the best ride smoothness for tough operating conditions
Pneumatic Counterbalance [10]	Using a compressed air cylinder instead of loads	Allows you to significantly reduce the weight and dimensions of ground equipment

Table 2

Methods of balancing a rocking machine by the method of diagnosing the condition

Method	Analysis parameter	Advantages and disadvantages
Current Method [12]	comparison of peak motor current values (I_{up}, I_{down}) during up and down travel	Simple to implement, but has low sensitivity and high error [3]
Power Method [1,14]	active power consumption of the motor (P)	High accuracy; allows calculating energy efficiency [3]
Torque Method: [5,6,12]	net torque on the gearbox shaft (T_{net}) based on the dynamogram and kinematics of the VK	The most accurate technical method; requires knowledge of VC kinematics
Slip Method [12,13]	Instantaneous change in rotor speed (ω) of the VK electric drive during the cycle	Allows sensorless diagnostics based on engine characteristics [13]

Methods for diagnosing SHPU, a thorough analysis of which is given in [15], were mainly considered from the point of view of monitoring and diagnosing the technical condition of both individual SHPU units and the installation as a whole. The most common methods for diagnosing SHPU are dynamometric, wattmeterographic and their modifications, as well as vibration [15]. At the same time, the unbalance of the rocking machine as a defect or malfunction affecting the change in the shape of the dynamogram and, as a consequence, the result of the diagnosis, i.e., the diagnosis, was not considered.

It should be noted that unbalance causes asymmetry of surface dynamograms: a shift in the load line, "humps" on the upstroke/downstroke or negative areas. This was previously perceived as a secondary effect, but modern studies emphasize its role in energy losses. At the same time, with proper balancing, the surface dynamogram approaches the shape of a parallelogram with minimal asymmetry. The characteristic features of such a dynamogram are the absence of pronounced "humps" or negative sections, the loading and unloading lines are almost parallel, and the peak torque on the gearbox is minimal with a peak torque ratio upstroke/downstroke ≈ 1 .

This shape ensures minimal energy consumption and uniform load on the gearbox.

At the same time, the specified methods (except vibration) can be used to control the unbalance of the

rocking machine. Let us consider their use to solve the specified problem.

Dynamometric method (based on dynamometer and counterweight moment).

A surface dynamometer card is a graphical representation of the dependence of the load on the polished rod (PPRL) on its movement during the full rocking cycle of the rocking machine. This curve, traditionally obtained using a dynamometer, reflects the resulting effect of all forces acting on the SHPU system, including the weight of the rods, hydrostatic fluid pressure, inertial and frictional forces, as well as the counterbalance effect (CBE).

The dynamometric method, known as the counterbalance moment method (CBM), is a standard industry approach for in-depth analysis of SHPU operation [16, 17]. Its principle is to combine measured data from the surface dynamogram (a graph of the dependence of the load on the polished rod on its position) with calculated parameters [18]. To calculate the net torque, the following are used:

- dynamograph data: measured over time of the load and position of the polished rod;
- torque factors: calculated values that depend on the exact geometric parameters of the rocking machine (length of the balancer, crank, connecting rod, etc.) and translate the linear load on the rod into torque on the gearbox shaft;

- torque from counterweights: calculated based on the mass, type and position of the counterweights on the cranks.

Advantages of the dynamometric method:

- ensuring the highest accuracy and deep understanding of the physical processes occurring in the system "well - pump - rods - rocking machine";
- the ability to calculate not only the net moment, but also its components.

The disadvantages of the method are:

- significant complexity associated with the installation of specialized equipment (dynamograph) on the polished rod, which requires stopping the rocking machine;
- high sensitivity to the accuracy of determining the geometric parameters of the installation, which may be unknown or difficult to access"
- possible errors in measuring the load on the polished rod using a dynamograph can lead to incorrect conclusions about the state of balance of the rocking machine;

Static Method (Counterbalance Effect, CBE)

Balancing a rocking machine involves adjusting the counterbalance torque to minimize peak gearbox torque and to ensure uniform loading of the drive during the upstroke and downstroke.

Traditionally, optimal balance is achieved when the effective counterbalance on the polished rod is approximately equal to the buoyant rod weight plus half the fluid load on the plunger (fluid load/2). The static Counterbalance Effect (CBE) test is a direct method of determining the torque generated by the counterbalances. The procedure involves stopping the rocking machine in a position where the cranks are horizontal and then releasing the brake. The rod load at which the system remains stationary is used to calculate the counterbalance torque [9,19].

This method has significant drawbacks that limit its application:

- inability to apply in case of severe imbalance: if the installation is significantly unbalanced, it is impossible to hold it in a static position;
- influence of static friction and inertia: These factors introduce a significant error in the measurement, since the test is static, not dynamic;
- rapid fluid leakage: in pumps with significant leakage, the load on the rod changes rapidly, which does not allow for a correct static measurement.

To estimate the torque in the gearbox, standard calculations according to the API 11E method are traditionally used, which are based on measuring the load on the polished rod and taking into account the geometric parameters of the installation together with the mass of the counterweights [8,20]. However, this method requires accurate knowledge of the position of the counterweights, which often requires personnel to go directly to the well [5,20].

As an alternative, methods based on the analysis of the behavior of the electric motor and the measurement of its instantaneous power [5,8,20] are considered - wattmeter methods. Measurement of electrical parameters allows you to quickly determine the state of balance without a detailed description of the installation geometry [5,11,20].

Wattmeter methods and torque-angle maps

Wattmeter methods are more versatile than dynamometric ones, as they carry more information about the electric drive of the SHPU and about the state of the components of the pumping machine. Wattmeter methods allow for simpler and more reliable automatic control of the SHPU, remote transmission of time diagrams, and also to obtain statistical information about the SHPU operation for further processing.

Wattmeter methods (motor power-based diagnostics) are based on the analysis of the electrical parameters of the pumping machine drive - power consumption, current and voltage of the electric motor. These methods allow for indirect assessment of the mechanical characteristics of the SHPU units without direct measurement of the load on the polished rod (polished rod load).

The wattmeter reflects the nature of the change in tangential forces acting on the crank shaft, from the weight of the rods, loads on the crank and balancer, from the oscillations of the rods in the liquid, from inertial forces due to the loads on the balancer and crank. The main disadvantage of this method is the influence of the kinematic scheme of the rocking machine on the useful signal (from the point of view of the passage of the useful signal from the submersible pump, the kinematic scheme of the rocking machine works as a low-pass filter). This disadvantage can also be considered an advantage, since at the same time the condition of the rocking machine itself is diagnosed, in particular its balance. In addition, according to the known parameters of the kinematic scheme of the rocking machine, its influence on the load signal shape can be fully compensated [14,15].

The main advantage is the possibility of continuous monitoring using standard equipment (wattmeters, frequency converters), which reduces capital costs and increases reliability in field conditions [9,19].

For practical implementation of wattmeterographic methods, it is advisable to determine the masses of balancing loads for the kinematic scheme of replacement of the rocking machine. The solution of this problem can be carried out using the experimental-analytical method, first proposed in [14,15]. Its essence lies in the numerical selection of the mass of the loads according to the known experimental simultaneously recorded dynamographic and wattmeterographic dependencies. For each value of the test mass, the wattmeterogram is calculated according to the dynamographic data and compared with the experimental wattmeterographic dependence - by finding the correlation coefficient. The mass value is selected for which the correlation coefficient value is maximum.

Experimental studies conducted on the wells of the Carpathian region allowed us to verify the above considerations regarding the possibility of automated determination of the masses of balancing loads - based on the simultaneous recording of dynamographic and wattmeterographic data. For the B-320 well, equipped with a SKN-10 3312 type rocking machine, the following dependencies were obtained as a result of the calculations (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Wattmetergrams: 1 measured experimentally, 2 calculated for a mass of 2400 kg, 3 calculated for a mass of 2340 kg

In this case, the correlation coefficient is $K_k=0.902$ with a load mass on the crank of 2340 kg.

The correlation coefficient was calculated for a certain range of load masses, presented in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Graph of the dependence of the correlation coefficient K_k on the mass of the load on the crank m_2 for well B 320

Similar results were obtained for other wells, which confirms the possibility of using the proposed method to determine the unknown masses of balancing loads. It should be noted that the method under consideration is widely used in foreign practice today.

A key tool of wattmeterographic methods is also the torque-angle dynamogram (torque vs crank angle card), which reflects the dependence of the net torque on the gearbox shaft (net gearbox torque) on the crank angle (crank angle, θ , from 0° to 360°). Such a card is more sensitive to the state of equilibrium than the classical surface dynamogram, since it directly reflects energy losses and peak loads on the gearbox.

The net torque at the gearbox (T_{net}) is calculated from the instantaneous power of the electric motor (P_{motor}) and the angular velocity of the crank (ω):

$$T_{net} = (P_{motor} - P_{losses}) / \omega,$$

where P_{losses} are losses in the motor and transmission (magnetic, mechanical, electrical), which are

estimated using efficiency maps or empirical correlations.

A more accurate approach uses three-phase current and voltage measurements to calculate active power:

$$P_{motor} = \sqrt{3} \times U \times I \times \cos \varphi,$$

where U is the line voltage, I is the current, and $\cos \varphi$ is the power factor.

The angular velocity ω is determined by the kinematics of the rocking machine (taking into account the motor speed and the gear ratio). In modern systems with VFD (variable frequency drive), these parameters are available in real time [21].

The shape of the torque-angle map at optimal balancing

With correct balancing, the net torque is symmetrical about the axis $\theta = 180^\circ$. The peak values on the upstroke (rise, $\theta \approx 0^\circ-180^\circ$) and downstroke (descent, $\theta \approx 180^\circ-360^\circ$) are approximately equal in absolute

value, but opposite in sign. The curve has no negative sections of significant duration, and the peak torque is minimal.

Characteristic features:

- symmetry of the peaks (peak torque ratio ≈ 1);

- absence of pronounced negative moments (the motor operates in the generator mode minimally);
- minimal RMS torque, which correlates with low energy consumption.

Example of a perfectly balanced torque-angle map [18] (Fig. 3,4).

Fig. 3. Comparison of pure torques with and without inertial effects.

Fig. 4. Comparison of net torques for two optimization criteria

Effect of underbalance (underbalanced condition)

With insufficient counterbalance, the peak positive torque on the upstroke significantly exceeds the negative torque on the downstroke. The curve shifts into the positive region, with a pronounced negative torque at the end of the downstroke (regenerative braking).

Characteristic features:

- Asymmetry with dominance of positive torque.
- Negative peak on the downstroke ($\theta \approx 270^\circ - 360^\circ$).
- Increase in peak torque by 20–50%, which increases the risk of gearbox overload and energy consumption.

Examples of underbalanced torque-angle maps [9, 22] (Fig. 5,6).

Fig. 5. Comparison of the polished rod's and the plunger's movement for an unanchored tubing string.

Fig. 6. Measured and calculated electrical power diagram of well X1.

Effect of overbalanced condition.

With excessive counterbalance, the situation is the opposite: negative torque dominates on the upstroke, with a pronounced positive peak on the downstroke.

Characteristic features:

- Shift of the curve into the negative region.

- Negative torque on the upstroke ($\theta \approx 90^\circ-180^\circ$).
- Increased regenerative braking, which complicates engine control.

Examples of overbalanced conditions [23] (Fig. 7,8).

Fig. 5. Torque curve of conventional pumping units

Torque curve of conventional pumping units

Fig. 6. Crank balance torque for conventional pump units.

Quantitative assessment of balance by torque-angle map. The degree of balance is assessed by the ratio of peak moments:

$$Peak\ torque\ ratio = \frac{|T_{max_up}|}{|T_{max_down}|} \approx 1 \text{ (optimally),}$$

Or for RMS torque:

$$T_{rms} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} T_{net}^2(\theta) d\theta},$$

whose minimization is the criterion for optimal balance.

Advantages and limitations of wattmeter methods

Advantages:

- Low cost and continuous data availability.
- Higher sensitivity to balance (compared to load-displacement).

• Integration with ML for automated classification [21].

Limitations:

- Need for accurate loss calibration (P_{losses}).

- Influence of variations in mains voltage and motor temperature.

- Lower accuracy at low loads.

Today, a promising direction is the combination of API 11E calculations with drive motor power analysis, which allows determining the real torque on the gearbox shaft of the pumping machine in real time, using only telemetry data without the need for physical measurements of the position of the counterweights in place [12].

According to sources, this combined approach is implemented as follows:

1. Mechanical Basis: API 11E Calculations

The API 11E method is the industry standard for static moment analysis. It is based on the use of the torque factor (TF), an imaginary lever arm that depends on the geometry of the machine-rocking machine linkages [2].

• Net torque: Calculated as the difference between the moment due to the rod load and the moment due to the counterweights:

$$T_{net} = TF \times (F - SU) - MCB \sin(\theta)$$

where F is the load, SU is the structural unbalance, MCB is the moment due to the counterweights [2,25].

Limitations: For an accurate calculation using this formula, it is necessary to know the exact weight and position of the counterweights (CBT/CBE), which usually requires a trip to the well.

2. Electrical base: Motor power analysis

The power supplied to the motor is directly proportional to the torque at the gearbox [2].

• Torque calculation from power: The relationship

$$TN = 9.53 \times (kW \times Eff) / (SPM \times SV)$$

is used, where kW is the instantaneous power, Eff is the transmission efficiency, SPM is the swing frequency, SV is the speed variation [2,16].

Advantage: Power data can be easily obtained remotely via wattmetering, which reflects the dynamic behavior of the system [10,16].

3. Combination algorithm (Hybrid method)

The latest methods propose to combine these approaches to eliminate the shortcomings of each of them [12]. The process consists of the following steps:

1. Determination of the unbalance factor: Based on the electrical indicators (wattmeterogram), the load ratio between the up and down stroke is calculated [12].

2. Calculation of the "ideal" torque according to API 11E: Using the telemetric dynamogram, the theoretical torque is calculated for the current conditions without taking into account the actual position of the loads [12].

3. Correlation: Since the dynamics of the engine power qualitatively repeats the torque changes, the unbalance factor from the electrical model is superimposed on the mechanical API 11E model [12].

4. Inference: By combining these data, the system "guesses" (infers) the actual counterweight torque (CBT) that would correspond to the power consumption, which allows to obtain an accurate torque diagram of the gearbox [12].

Advantages of the combined approach

• High accuracy: The combination allows to reduce the error of the torque calculation to a level of less than 10% (compared to an error of more than 30% when using only electrical models without knowledge of the motor curves) [12].

• No need for surveys: The method eliminates the need for manual measurement of the weight and position of the counterweights in the well [12].

• Inertia accounting: Real-time analysis of the motor allows to take into account the effects of inertia, which the static API 11E model usually ignores [12].

Here we can draw the following analogy: the API 11E standard gives us a "blueprint" of how the SHGNU units should work, and the analysis of the power of the drive motor of the pumping machine shows how the installation is actually "stressed". Combining them, we see a complete picture of the load on the internal parts of the gearbox without disassembling it.

As noted above, an important diagnostic tool is dynamometry, which provides information about the load

on the rod at each point of the stroke. The use of mathematical models, in particular the Gibbs wave equation, allows the calculation of underground dynamograms to detect pump defects, gas influence or liquid shocks [2,6,20]. Modern approaches also suggest optimizing the balance not only by peak moments, but also by minimizing the cyclic load factor (CLF) [6].

The minimum value of CLF provides the smoothest load on the gearbox, which allows the use of lower-power motors and increases the service life of the equipment [6].

Innovative solutions in the industry include the development of intelligent automatic control devices that can independently change the position of the counterweights based on real-time data [1,3]. To increase the accuracy of diagnostics, a power integration method is proposed that takes into account energy consumption both during direct travel and during engine operation in recuperation mode [13]. In addition, the introduction of secondary balancing systems allows for additional smoothing of torque fluctuations and reduction of the root mean square load [4]. Experimental studies confirm that proper balancing using such devices can reduce energy consumption by 8–10% [1,3].

Today, the development of intelligent control systems has led to the emergence of sensorless diagnostic methods, the use of which will allow solving the problems of both operational control and balancing of pumping machines, and controlling the process of mechanized oil production using SHPU, taking into account their technical condition.

The intellectualization of the process of mechanized oil production using SHPU at the current stage includes:

- Power Integration Method: Instead of comparing peak values, modern systems calculate the integral of the energy consumed per upstroke and downstroke [13]. This avoids errors caused by random load fluctuations.

- Intelligent Controllers based on Smart Sucker Rod Pump (SSRP) technology, the use of which allows for the independent determination of the degree of imbalance using wattmeterograms and the automatic movement of counterweights to achieve minimum energy consumption in real time without stopping the well [1,24], as well as the analysis of the form of detection of defects (rod breakage, leaks in valves, gas impact, etc.);

- Artificial Intelligence Algorithms: The use of the Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) method allows for the optimization of the counterweight configuration to minimize the cyclic load factor (CLF) [6,10].

- Dynamic Simulation: New models (2021) take into account the rotor moment of inertia and elastic deformations of the rod string, which increases the accuracy of the calculation of the net torque on the gearbox by 5% compared to the static API 11E standard [6,10].

Finally, let's consider the relationship between the parameters of balance and energy efficiency.

It was noted above that the imbalance of the rocking machine leads to significant torque fluctuations and the appearance of negative torque when the energy of the counterweights exceeds the needs of the system.

This forces the engine to operate in generator mode. How does this affect:

1. *Energy consumption*: The implementation of intelligent monitoring systems and correction of the position of loads allows to achieve energy savings in the range of 8–14% (on average 11%) [11, 12, 20].

2. *Motor load*: With insufficient balancing (Under-balanced), the current peak is observed during the upward stroke; with excessive (Over-balanced) - during the downward stroke [26]. Optimal balancing minimizes the root-mean-square value of the current and heat losses in the motor windings [8].

3. *Energy regeneration*: Modern drives with active front-end cascade (AFE), such as LUFKIN REGEN™, allow to return up to 11.9% of the consumed energy to the network instead of dissipating it in the form of heat in the braking resistors.

4. *Gearbox life*: An increase in peak torque by 10% above the nominal value halves the gearbox life, and an overload of 20% reduces it by up to 80% [11,26].

Conclusions.

Traditional analysis of the impact of balancing on the surface dynamogram demonstrates that asymmetry is the primary indicator of torque imbalance, with direct consequences for energy consumption and equipment life. This laid the foundation for modern automated methods.

Imbalance transforms the dynamogram through dynamic distortions (Rod Float, vibrations), which requires the use of advanced mathematical models (Gibbs wave equation in combination with Everitt-Jennings algorithms) and artificial intelligence for the correct interpretation of the technical condition of the SHPU.

Wattmetrographic methods with torque-angle maps are an effective alternative to classic dynamograms, providing more accurate diagnostics of balancing and the potential for real-time optimization. This opens the way to reducing operating costs by 10–20%.

The transition from static calculations to dynamic models and the use of intelligent automatic balancing systems (SSRP) not only provides energy savings of up to 50%, but also significantly extends the installation's maintenance interval due to the uniform distribution of the gearbox torque load.

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